

Antimicrobial resistance and untreated wastewater: Review of research carried out on Enterobacteriaceae in urban water bodies in Bolivia

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Abstract

Untreated urban wastewater poses a serious risks for the population in Bolivia, given the cocktail of pollutants and the resistance to antibiotics identified in microorganisms. Studies in La Paz and Cochabamba, and areas relevant to urban populations such as the Titicaca and the Amazon region, suggest that the issue is rapidly spreading. Weak regulations and legal mechanisms, would provide means to face the growing challenge.

Keywords

Untreated urban wastewater; urban rivers; Latin America

INTRODUCTION

Coliform bacteria, particularly *Escherichia coli*, are indicators of fecal contamination and possible pathogens in water. In urban areas of Bolivia, public health related to wastewater management pose important challenges, given the rapid urbanization and inadequate sanitation infrastructure (Cossio et al., 2021; Contraloría General del Estado, 2014). As a consequence, several cities face potential threats because of the cocktail of pollutants found in rivers (Contraloría General del Estado, 2014; Salazar et al., 2019; Medina et al., 2021; Quillaguamán et al., 2021; Rocha-Melogno et al., 2020).

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) has become a global health crisis and its prevalence in wastewater systems is a growing concern. In Bolivia, the misuse and overuse of antibiotics in both human and veterinary medicine have accelerated the development of resistant bacterial strains (Guzman-Otazo et al., 2019). Untreated urban wastewater flowing towards river courses and canals serve as a reservoir for resistant microorganisms, facilitating the spread of AMR genes (Salazar et al., 2019; Guzman-Otazo et al., 2019; Medina et al., 2021; Quillaguamán et al., 2021).

In 2019 there were 2500 deaths attributable to AMR and 10100 deaths associated with AMR in Bolivia, placing the country among the 50 countries (of 240 evaluated) with the highest mortality rate per 100000 inhabitants associated with AMR, surpassing the number of deaths from diabetes, kidney diseases, respiratory infections and tuberculosis, diseases (IHME, 2023). AMR is therefore a complex challenge for public health, becoming a regional transdisciplinary and cross-border problem due to the river network connectivity with neighbouring countries.

METHODS

The literature review was carried under the recommendations of Page et al. (2021), as follows: definition of the objective and purpose, identification of trends, causes, and mitigation alternatives. Scientific databases used were PubMed, Scopus, Mendeley and Research4Life. Keywords combined terms such as "AMR", "resistance mechanisms", "interventions" and terms associated with the geographical scope. The quality of the information was judged based on the questions: Does the study directly address the research question?, were methods properly applied?; is the study design adequate?; are the methods and results clearly presented?. The discussion was evaluated, based on the criteria of its context, the timeliness of the results, the implications, limitations and possible directions for future research.

IMPLICATIONS AND SOURCES OF AMR

Studies in Bolivia indicate that the discharge of resistant microorganisms into natural water bodies can alter local ecosystems (Agramont et al., 2020). Furthermore, the presence of antimicrobial-resistant pathogens in the environment increases the risk of reintroducing these resistant strains to human populations through water sources used for drinking and irrigation (Guzman-Otazo et al., 2019). Public health ramifications are also significant. Accordingly, in Bolivia where healthcare resources are very limited, the burden of AMR could overwhelm currently overstretched medical facilities, suggesting that treatment protocols will get more complex, increasing healthcare costs.

The country has a legal-regulatory framework under the Political Constitution of the State, the Medicines Law 1737 (1996), the Regulations of the Medicines Law D.S. 25235 (1998), the National and Single Supply System D.S. 26873 (2019), the Regulation of the National and Single Supply System R.M. 0735 (2002), the Manual for the Administration of the FIM Municipal Institutional Pharmacy (2007) and the Manual for the Application of Insurance Benefits of the Ministry of Health (2015), with support from the authority who regulates the use of medicines AGEMED (State Agency for Medicines and Health Technologies) (Ministry of Health, 2016). Nevertheless, the literature urges for coordinated actions (Vera Carrasco, 2020).

Sources of antimicrobial resistance

From an engineering perspective, the main responsible of the AMR emergence in Bolivian wastewater is the insufficient infrastructure for the safe management of urban waste and the weaknesses of existing legal instruments. However, the most concerning issue results from the serious deficiencies to regulate the use, prescription and access to antibiotics, which currently can be purchased without prescriptions in local stores, informal street vendors and drug stores, currently supported by an illegal medicine business which generates around 20 million dollars per year according to the Chamber of the Bolivian Pharmaceutical Industry (Guarachi, 2023).

PREVALENCE OF AMR IN URBAN WATER BODIES IN BOLIVIA

AMR in urban areas of La Paz and Cochabamba

Studies report the presence of AMR in bodies of water in Bolivia. Attention has been focused on the cities of La Paz and Cochabamba; however, there are also studies on Andean lakes and other systems relevant to urban areas. In the Choqueyapu and La Paz rivers (La Paz, 755732 inhabitants), Rocha River and Laguna Alalay (Cochabamba, 856198 inhabitants), it has been found antibiotic-resistant bacteria, including *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) and enterococcus, frequently detected in samples from water bodies and bioaerosols. Resistance levels were high, suggesting downstream pollution as a result of inexistent wastewater treatment facilities.

AMR in the Choqueyapu River has revealed significant concerns. The river is a reservoir for several antibiotic-resistant bacteria, which threat populations downstream which use that water for drinking, irrigation, and recreation (Ginn et al., 2021; Guzman-Otazo et al., 2019; Rocha-Melogno et al., 2020). In the Choqueyapu River it was identified resistance to sulfamethoxazole and amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, with presence of coliforms in 73% and 60% of the samples (Salazar et al., 2020). A subsequent study carried out during the dry season, determined an increase in antibiotic resistance for tetracycline, gentamicin and ciprofloxacin, and a reduction for sulfamethoxazole-trimethoprim, meropenem and amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (Medina et al., 2021). At the gene level, bioaerosols in the vicinity found that the majority of air samples (82%) had detectable targets above the experimentally determined detection limit. (Ginn et al., 2021). The threat of AMR was also identified in soil and crops samples taken at the river outlet, suggesting a high potential risk of transmission of diarrheal diseases (Guzman-Otazo et al., 2019).

In Cochabamba, RAM studies provided similar results. The Rocha River is polluted by untreated sewage, agricultural runoff, and industrial discharges. As in La Paz, Flores et al. (2019) identified *E. coli* producing ESBL and probably AmpC in the waters of the Tamborada and Rocha rivers, which are sources for the drinkingwater and irrigation systems. Concerns have also spread to the city's main urban lagoon (Alalay lagoon), where water and sediment samples found a large number

of genes related to bacterial virulence, where the majority of virulence genes and AMR detected can cause serious infections (Quillaguamán et al., 2021).

AMR in Lake Titicaca and the Beni and Mamoré rivers

Although outside the urban area, which is where this article was initially proposed, it is valid to cite studies carried out in the Katari River basin and rivers of the Bolivian Amazon because agricultural-livestock production is transported to supply the main cities of Bolivia. In those systems, the presence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria has been identified, related to inadequate wastewater treatment facilities and agricultural runoff.

In the Katari River basin, fecal contamination has been identified as the main driver of high levels of AMR in environments contaminated by wastewater and mining activities; There, the presence of the problem was emphasized in Milluni Chico (drinking water supply system for the La Paz-El Alto systems) and Uru Uru (in the area of influence of the city of Oruro, 570,194 inhabitants) (Agramont et al. , 2020). The implications of these findings are serious, particularly for communities that rely on the river for drinking water and irrigation, emphasizing the critical need for access to clean water and improved sanitation practices.

Further to the Amazon basin, a worrying finding is the identification of wastewater bacterial species in the metagenomes of rivers (Quillaguamán et al., 2024). Diseases associated with the presence of *Arcobacter butzleri* were identified, although clinical evaluation were still required. There were also identified resistant genes to multiple antibiotics, constituting a threat to the population living near rivers, resulting from inexistent wastewater treatment facilities in the area.

Regulations at the government level to face the challenge and final conclusions

AMR is a growing challenge in Latin America, which has led to the implementation of various legal regulations to address this public health problem. A key intervention area has been the regulation of the use of antibiotics in agriculture and livestock. In many countries in the region, the administration of antibiotics to farm animals has been a common practice, used both to prevent disease and to promote growth. However, various legislations have begun to restrict this practice, limiting the use of antibiotics to situations of diagnosed disease and prohibiting the free sale of these medications.

In the field of human health, several countries have adopted laws that regulate the prescribing and dispensing of antibiotics. These regulations seek to reduce self-prescription and inappropriate use of antibiotics in clinics and hospitals. In Latin America, protocols have been established for the prescription of antibiotics in the public health system, promoting the education of health professionals on the rational use of these medications. In addition, awareness campaigns aimed at the population have been implemented to promote the responsible use of antibiotics.

Surveillance and monitoring of antibiotic resistance has also been an important focus in legal regulations. Several countries have created surveillance systems to track the prevalence of resistant bacteria in hospitals, communities, and agricultural settings. This information is crucial for effective policy formulation and evidence-based decision making.

International and regional cooperation is essential to address antibiotic resistance effectively, as the problem has a magnitude that exceeds the local scale. Initiatives such as the WHO Global Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance promote collaboration between countries to share good practices and develop coherent policies. In this sense, Latin America has begun to strengthen cooperation between governments, non-governmental organizations and the private sector to implement and enforce the necessary regulations. This collaboration is essential to ensure a comprehensive approach that not only addresses antibiotic use but also considers the socioeconomic factors that contribute to resistance.

Latin America faces significant challenges in the fight against antibiotic resistance, but emerging legal regulations represent a positive step toward mitigating this problem. The implementation of

regulations focused on the use of antibiotics in agriculture, human health, and resistance surveillance are essential to protect public health and preserve the effectiveness of antimicrobial treatments in the future. Cooperation between countries and continuing education are as well relevant, because they are essential elements for the success of these initiatives.

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